

Symptoms and plant height reduction at 3 WAI, and grain yield reduction in plants of 6 cultivars infected at 1 wk after soaking, with RTBV + RTSV, RTBV alone, or RTSV alone. IRRI, 1988.

Cultivar	Virus	Symptoms ^a	Height reduction (%)	Yield reduction (%)
Balimau Putih	RTBV + RTSV	-	9.2	19.9
	RTBV	-	3.3	17.1
	RTSV	-	1.5	7.2
BW272-6B	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, D	62.6	94.2
	RTBV	S, Y	59.4	81.9
	RTSV	-	16.3	14.5
FK135	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, I, D	72.0	99.0
	RTBV	S, Y, I, D	68.2	98.0
	RTSV	-	2.9	19.5
Palasithari	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, I	36.9	33.5
	RTBV	S, Y	34.6	20.6
	RTSV	-	4.5	10.1
Sigadis	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, I	16.9	30.7
	RTBV	-	13.5	23.9
	RTSV	-	11.2	9.1
Utri Rajapan	RTBV + RTSV	s, t	29.4	28.8
	RTBV	-	21.8	16.8
	RTSV	-	2.3	1.6
TNI	RTBV + RTSV	S, Y, I	71.8	97.4
	RTBV	S, Y, I	49.1	94.7
	RTSV	-	3.7	19.5

^aS = severe stunting, s = mild stunting, Y = yellow orange discoloration, y = mild yellowing, I = inter-veinal chlorosis, D = drooping of leaves, t = reduced tillering, - (dash) = no clear symptoms.

Frequency distribution of infection rates and scores of 1,117 rice germplasm tested by the modified mass screening method. IRRI, 1988.

Using these results, we modified the greenhouse mass screening method as follows:

1. Seed 20 germinated seeds of each entry in a pot.
2. Allow vector leafhoppers (GLH) to feed 3-4 d on RTV-infected plants.
3. Confine 7- to 10-d-old seedlings of 16 entries in a cage with 8-10 viruliferous GLH/ seedling for 3 h.
4. Consecutively inoculate 2 additional sets of entries.
5. Allow the viruliferous GLH to feed overnight on RTV-infected plants,

then use them again for inoculation.

6. Score seedlings individually 3-4 WAI.

Score symptom severity as follows:

- 1 = no symptoms
 - 3 = 1-10% plant height reduction with no leaf discoloration
 - 5 = 11-30% plant height reduction with no distinct leaf discoloration
 - 7 = 31-50% plant height reduction and/ or yellow to orange leaf discoloration
 - 9 = more than 50% plant height reduction and yellow to orange leaf discoloration
7. Compute average score.
 8. Select all entries for which average score is lower than 4 and index plants in ELISA for presence of RTBV and RTSV.

Cultivars with scores lower than 3 were considered resistant (or tolerant); cultivars with scores of 5, moderately resistant. We tested more than 1,000 rice germplasm using this modified mass screening method. Nine percent had

scores 0-3 (see figure). Tjempo Kijik (Acc. no. 16602) and Utri Merah (Acc. no. 16682) exhibited very mild symptoms but had high infection with RTBV and/or RTSV. □

Reaction of rice to yellow dwarf disease (YDD) and green leafhopper (GLH)

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To identify sources of resistance to YDD and its GLH vector *Nephotettix virescens*, seedlings of 35 rice varieties were inoculated by 5 YDD-viruliferous leafhoppers per plant for 24 h. The varieties also were tested against GLH, using the standard bulk seedling damage rating test.

Popular local rice varieties showed high susceptibility to the YDD pathogen (41.7-100% infection). NLR139-69, RP1931-54, and Tadukan had no infection. RP1931-54 and Tadukan also were resistant to GLH. NLR139-69 was resistant to YDD infection but susceptible to GLH. Kalinga-1 showed high resistance to GLH but 25% YDD infection. IR20, IR50, and TKM6 were resistant to GLH but showed 83, 67, and 58% YDD infection, respectively. □

Genetic analysis of bacterial blight (BB) resistance in Madhya Pradesh, India

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We evaluated about 7,000 rice accessions being maintained at Zonal Rice Research Station, Raipur, for field resistance to BB in 1982, when BB natural infection was very severe. The 204 entries found to be relatively free of disease were tested for resistance to 4 Philippine races of BB at Los Baños in

Reaction to BB race of F₁^a and F₂ populations from crosses of TN1 and IR22 with 35 cultivars from Madhya Pradesh, India.

Variety	Accession no.	Reaction ^a			
		F ₂ of crosses with TN1			F ₂ of crosses with IR22 ^b
		R (no.)	S (no.)	X ² :1	
					R (no.)
Badshahbhog	B2486	410	123	0.95	614
Bhatagunda	B2835	811	252	0.88	614
Bhatapyagi	B2352	655	229	0.33	806
Kalchi	K2096	376	144	1.87	720
Kanthbhulau	K2579	403	140	0.13	640
Kondi	K1655	370	164	2.33	580
Munagi	M1172	522	180	0.12	464
No. 19	N658	436	140	0.11	324
Agyasal	A330	459	170	1.27	464
Agyad	A544	580	211	1.09	684
Anj ania	A88-2	266	98	0.61	464
Aodiayasela	A509	333	128	1.73	600
Baidahuda	B2221	625	242	3.76	624
Baigan	B970	319	103	0.05	640
Bhonduparewa	B1141-1	274	94	0.03	570
Bhubhusi	B1617	576	179	0.60	544
Cross 116	C615	292	92	0.17	392
Dhaniyaphool	D514	598	205	0.09	605
Dhoulimatia	D800	898	264	3.10	680
Dubraj	D61-11	471	146	0.51	980
Dudga	D116-1	282	113	2.55	836
Dudhsar	D350	658	233	0.56	960
Gang prasad	G760	630	231	1.44	678
Garang	G705	432	143	0.00	640
Gonda	G600	684	206	1.53	706
Hansraj	H175	598	195	0.05	456
Jhili	J273	587	221	2.25	504
Kalmigurmatia	K589	301	87	1.24	488
Karigurmatia	K1191	332	128	1.81	480
Karrigurmatia	K1393	358	144	3.44	520
Lalianjan	L1206	328	120	0.63	520
Laligurmatia	L1267	433	142	0.01	756
Sarpin	S1436	597	226	2.52	720
Aagyasal	A456	599	220	1.41	480
Aagyasar	A518	619	186	1.44	800

^a R = resistant, S = susceptible. All F₁s of crosses with TN1 were R. ^b None segregated for susceptibility.

the 1984 wet season. Only 55 were resistant to race 1, only 1 was resistant to race 2. We analyzed 35 varieties resistant to race 1 genetically.

The 35 were crossed with TN1, which is susceptible to all Philippine races of BB. The F₁ and F₂ progenies were inoculated with race 1. All F₁ progenies were resistant; the F₂ populations segregated in the ratio 3 resistant: 1 susceptible (see table). This shows that resistance in those varieties is governed by single dominant genes.

The patterns of reaction to four Philippine races (R, S, S, MR) are similar to the reactions of IR22, which has the *Xa-4* gene for resistance. Therefore, we crossed the 35 varieties with IR22 and inoculated the F₁ and F₂ progenies with race 1. All F₁ progenies were resistant, as expected, and F₂ populations did not segregate for susceptibility (see table). These results show that the 35 varieties have the *Xa-4* gene for resistance. □

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Classification of leaf blast (B1) lesions

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Different types of B1 lesions are produced on rice leaves, depending on the combination of rice genotype and isolate of *Pyricularia oryzae*, plant age, and environmental conditions (see figure). Lesions are differentiated by shape, size, color, and absence or presence of sporulation.

The lesion type can be used as an indicator of the presence of compatible

isolates of the B1 pathogen or as a parameter to determine host and pathogen interaction. Although lesion type is recorded in conventional B1 nursery evaluations, the range is too narrow to illustrate all variations.

We developed a modified coding system to take into account the major lesion types (see table). Lesion type 1 indicates incompatible reactions of the host to a virulent isolate.

Lesion type 3 is often considered an incompatible reaction controlled by major genes, although the nature of the reaction is not well understood. Many japonica cultivars inoculated with indica

isolates produce type 3 lesions with yellow halo (see figure). Leaf B1 seldom increases when type 3 lesions predominate at the seedling stage. Quantitative evaluation based on type 3 lesions frequently fails to predict disease progress by other compatible isolates.

Lesion types 5, 7, and 9 are considered typical susceptible lesions produced by compatible isolates. Type 5 lesions are common on traditional upland rice cultivars. Disease progress, in general, is slower on cultivars with type 5 lesions than on cultivars with type 7 or 9 lesions. When disease pressure is high, lesions become bigger and many